

AN ANALYSIS OF THE NEUTRALISATION CURVES OF THE COLLOIDAL ACIDS. PART II

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The potentiometric and conductometric titration curves of some colloidal clay acids have been theoretically analysed. The analysis shows that the experimental curves for the two clay sols reflect a combination of two effects, viz., neutralisation of a polybasic acid in true solution and ion adsorption.

In a previous communication (Gupta, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 587), a model was proposed to explain the neutralisation curves of acid colloidal ion exchangers, and certain mathematical formulations were made on the basis of the model which were shown to fit satisfactorily with the experimental data of a silicic acid sol. The present paper seeks to explain some clay-acid titrations on the basis of the same model and assuming the same mathematical expressions derived there.

It has been shown (Part I) that the total acidity of the colloid can be divided into two parts, C_a and C_t , where C_a determines the amount of H^+ ions present in the micellar solution in a form available for exchange by other cations, the exchanged H^+ ions being subsequently neutralised by the OH^- ions of the added base present in the intermicellar solution, and C_t represents a polybasic acid forming the outer surface of the colloidal particles capable of direct neutralisation by the OH^- ions, the corresponding cations of the added base being present in the intermicellar solution. The cations replacing the H^+ ions in the micellar solution are supposed to be bound or adsorbed and do not record their activities on a corresponding reversible electrode. It has also been shown that the initial slope of the neutralisation curve of the colloidal polybasic acid, in which the active groups are distributed on a large surface, can be represented by a monobasic acid C_1 with a dissociation constant k_1 , where C_1 constitutes a fraction of the total intermicellar acidity, C_t . As the titration proceeds beyond C_1 , the value of the active monobasic acidity has to be increased to C_2 with a lower order dissociation constant, k_2 , to explain the next stretch, and so on. In this way the whole neutralisation curve may be approached when the last stretch of the curve may be represented by a monobasic acid, C_n , with a dissociation constant k_n , where $C_n = C_t$. The expression derived for the initial stretch, when a mono-acidic base like NaOH has been used for titration, is

$$p = C_a + \frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x} - \frac{x \cdot C_a}{\frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x}} - x \quad \dots (1)$$

where $x = (a_{H^+})_t$, i.e. the free or the intermicellar H^+ ion activity and K_w is the ionic product of water. For the second stretch the equation takes the form

$$p = C_a + \frac{C_2 k_2}{k_2 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x} - x \quad \dots (2)$$

and for subsequent stretches (C_3, k_3), (C_4, k_4) etc. replace (C_2, k_2) in the above equation.

The necessary experimental data presented here for the purpose of evaluation and comparison have been obtained from the works of Mitra (*Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 555). The abscissas in the curves have been recalculated in terms of normality of the added base and shown as such in the figures to facilitate comparison between the calculated and the experimental values.

In applying the above formulations, the initial p_H has been calculated from the slope of the curve and a slight parallel elevation of the evaluated curve has been observed in many cases (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*), the coincidence in some cases being accidental as in the following titration of a clay sol.

Sol C₁.—This sol was isolated from Ganges silt by electro dialysis of the clay fraction which was previously treated with 6% H₂O₂ and leached with 0.05 N-HCl. The resulting sol contained 0.72 g. of the colloid per litre and had an average p_H of 5.05. Its ultrafiltrate analysis showed no trace of Cl⁻ ion so that free hydrochloric acid was absent. The acid at inflexion was read at 1.91×10^{-5} N for titration with NaOH and 5.7×10^{-5} N with Ba(OH)₂. The curves are shown in Fig. 1.

The equation (1) has been found to apply up to range PQ, and for subsequent

stretches, *i.e.* QR, RS and ST, equation (2) has been applied with necessary C and k values evaluated from the slope. The initial H⁺ ion concentration and the value of C_n (which is somewhat less than the inflexion point value) have been found to be 7.08×10^{-6} N corresponding to p_H 5.15 and 1.7×10^{-5} N respectively. Table I records the results of analysis, and the 'b' values, marked with asterisks, were taken for computing the curve shown in full line, which is also the experimental curve.

TABLE I

		$C_1 = 14.158 \times 10^{-6}$ N. $k_1 = 7.079 \times 10^{-6}$.					
p_H	5.15	5.25	5.50	5.75	6.01	6.50	
$b \times 10^6$	0.00*	4.03*	18.14*	23.87*	27.04	29.85	
		$C_2 = 45.36 \times 10^{-6}$ N. $k_2 = 3.893 \times 10^{-7}$.					
p_H	5.75	6.00	6.25	6.50	6.75		
$b \times 10^6$	23.37	28.72*	35.06*	41.71	46.91		
		$C_3 = 128.1 \times 10^{-6}$ N. $k_3 = 9.526 \times 10^{-8}$.					
p_H	6.00	6.25	6.50	6.75	7.00		
$b \times 10^6$	27.14*	35.00*	46.35*	61.15	79.42		
		$C_4 = 356.3 \times 10^{-6}$ N. $k_4 = 2.715 \times 10^{-8}$.					
p_H	6.50	6.75*	7.00	7.25			
$b \times 10^6$	44.87	64.04*	93.00*	115.6			

As has been shown earlier (Part I, *loc. cit.*), the evaluated dissociation constants are only averages, acting over a particular range, and do not represent any true constancy, because the fundamental assumption involved is that as the active intermicellar acidity increases, the dissociation constant drifts slowly to lower and lower values due to polybasicity of the colloid. The clay acid is fundamentally a weak acid having the dissociable groups $-\text{SiOH}$ or $-\text{AlOH}$ and the flat run approximately up to the inflexion point is a measure of the micellar or adsorbable H^+ ions, *i. e.* C_a , and does not signify any strong acid character.

The equation (1) cannot be applied to titrations with bivalent bases because the Donnan equilibrium involved in its deduction has to be modified accordingly. As the Donnan equilibrium is not significantly involved after the inflexion point, it is expected that the NaOH and $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ curves should be identical or, say, parallel in this region where we are concerned with neutralisation as in true solution, and equation (2) holds good. The $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ curve in Fig. 1, however, shows a greater extent of flat run than that due to NaOH and a continued flat portion after the inflexion point. This can be explained by the fact that the Ba^{2+} ions induce aggregation and thus increase the value of C_a , diminishing the value of C_f by a corresponding amount. A reference to the model in Part I (*loc. cit.*) will show that aggregation helps in the conversion of some of the intermicellar groups into micellar groups and the opposite effect takes place when an aggregate breaks up. Consequently, a greater amount of acidity at inflexion and a corresponding flat run were obtained by using a bivalent base like $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$. A slow process of continued aggregation with simultaneous removal of Ba^{2+} ions from the intermicellar solution will also account for the continued flattening even after the inflexion point which marks the saturation of the existing micellar groups.

Sol C.—This sol was also obtained from Ganges silt in the same way as sol C_1 , but in its isolation the hydrochloric acid pretreatment was omitted. Its colloid content was found to be 0.44 g. per litre and, peculiarly enough, its ultrafiltrate analysis showed the presence of free hydrochloric acid in a strength of $9.5 \times 10^{-5} N$ in the sol. As in the case of silicic acid sol, previously analysed (Part I, *loc. cit.*), we have to use here the corrected equations:

$$b = C_a + \frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x} + \tau - \frac{x, C_a}{\frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x} + \tau} - x \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

for the initial stretch, where $\tau = (a_{\text{Cl}} -)_f$, and

$$\phi = C_a + \tau + \frac{K_w}{x} + \frac{C_2 k_2}{k_2 + x} - x \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

etc. for the subsequent stretches. The value of $(C_a + \tau)$ has been evaluated at $24.5 \times 10^{-5} N$ from the curve shown in Fig. 2 (which is necessarily slightly less than the inflexion point value, $28.0 \times 10^{-5} N$, reported in the text) and since $\tau = 9.5 \times 10^{-5} N$, one gets $C_a = 15 \times 10^{-5} N$. The other evaluated constants and the results of analysis are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

$C_1 = 9.272 \times 10^{-5} N.$ $k_1 = 8.654 \times 10^{-6}.$					
p_{π}	4.0	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.0
$b \times 10^5$	0.0	19.20*	26.72*	30.68*	32.63
$(a_{Na^+})_f \times 10^5$	10.0	3.162	1.0	0.3162	0.100
$(a_{Na^+})_f \times 10^5$	0.0	8.33	12.80	15.97	17.71
$\kappa \times 10^5$	5.01	2.69	2.11	2.03	
$C_2 = 15.62 \times 10^{-5} N.$ $k_2 = 1.572 \times 10^{-6}.$					
p_{π}	5.5	5.825	6.5	7.0	
$b \times 10^5$	29.37	32.35*	37.2*	39.1	
$(a_{Na^+})_f \times 10^5$	0.3162	0.1496	0.03162	0.01	
$(a_{Na^+})_f \times 10^5$	14.37	17.35	22.1	24.1	
$\kappa \times 10^5$		2.053	2.317		
$C_3 = 23.72 \times 10^{-5} N.$ $k_3 = 3.442 \times 10^{-7}.$					
p_{π}	6.5	7.0	7.5	8.0	
$b \times 10^5$	36.85	42.88*	46.27*	47.55	
$(a_{Na^+})_f \times 10^5$	0.03162	0.01	0.00316	0.001	
$(a_{Na^+})_f \times 10^5$	21.84	27.88	31.27	32.55	
$\kappa \times 10^5$		2.667	2.88		

The 'b' values, marked with asterisks, show the full line theoretical curve in Fig. 2. The $(a_{Na^+})_f$ has also been evaluated from the electroneutrality relation,

$$\begin{aligned} (a_{Na^+})_f &= (a_{R^-})_f + (a_{OH^-})_f + (a_{Cl^-})_f - (a_{H^+})_f \\ &= \frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x} + r - x \quad \dots (5) \end{aligned}$$

for the initial stretch and replacing (C_1, k_1) in the above equation by (C_2, k_2) etc. for other stretches, and has been incorporated in the above table. The amount of Na^+ ion adsorbed at any p_{π} can also be computed, if necessary, from the relation $(a_{Na^+})_a = b - (a_{Na^+})_f$. The values for the specific conductivity (κ), shown in Table II, have been obtained from the relation

$$\kappa = \frac{U_{H^+} (a_{H^+})_f + U_{Na^+} (a_{Na^+})_f + V_{Cl^-} (a_{Cl^-})_f}{1000} \text{ mhos,}$$

neglecting the contributions due to OH^- ion in acid solution and the mobility of the sluggish colloid anions. The adsorbed H^+ and Na^+ ions being part of the micelle are supposed not to take part in the conduction of the current. The following limiting equivalent conductivities at 35° have been assumed for the different ionic species:

$$U_{H^+} = 404, U_{Na^+} = 64 \text{ and } V_{Cl^-} = 93, \text{ ohms}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}.$$

It will be seen from curve (a), Fig. 2, that the calculated conductivity curve from the evaluated potentiometric data has almost the same slope and shows the same rounded minimum as has been obtained experimentally, only the calculated curve is situated somewhat lower.

FIG. 2

SOL C

This is not surprising as the fact, that a discrepancy between the absolute values of ionic concentrations obtained from potentiometric and conductometric data occurs in these systems, is already well known, though the reason is still somewhat obscure. Also, the inherent difficulty in obtaining identical curves in these system by different measurements for the same titration has been emphasised by the parallel sets of potentiometric and conductometric experimental curves. These curves were obtained (Mitra, *loc. cit.*) by using a titration cell suitable for simultaneous conductometric and potentiometric measurements in conjunction with accessory instruments suitable for accurate work.

If we do not wish to neglect the mobility of the clay ions, then neglecting the small OH^- ion concentration, the formula for the specific conductivity κ becomes

$$\kappa = \frac{U_{\text{H}^+} (a_{\text{H}^+})_f + U_{\text{Na}^+} (a_{\text{Na}^+})_f + V_{\text{Cl}^-} (a_{\text{Cl}^-})_f + V_{\text{R}^-} (a_{\text{R}^+} + a_{\text{Na}^+} - a_{\text{Cl}^-})_f}{1000} \text{ mhos,}$$

where V_{R^-} represents the limiting equivalent conductivity of the clay particles for the ionised spots. Curve (b) in Fig. 2 shows the conductometric curve for this change accepting a small arbitrary value of $20 \text{ ohms}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Mukherjee *et al.*, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 517, 531) for the equivalent conductivity per equivalent of charge on the clay particles (cf. Gupta, *Science & Culture*, 1956, 21, 749; 22, 282; 1957, 22, 401).

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The abscissa for sol H/20 in Fig. 6 in Part I (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 537) should read 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20 for 0, 20, 40, 60, and 80